

Spontaneous Eruption of an Impacted Permanent Left Maxillary Central Incisor after the Surgical Removal of Multiple Impacted Supernumerary Teeth in a 10-year-Old boy, with a Diagnosis Confirmed by CBCT and Complete Follow-up of 14 Month

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Abstract

A failure of maxillary incisor eruption is commonly attributed to the presence of a supernumerary tooth. Multiple supernumerary teeth in the absence of any syndrome are not very common. The optimal timing of surgical removal of unerupted anterior supernumerary teeth is often conjectural. An atraumatic careful surgical procedure is important to prevent any damage to the developing roots. The majority of impacted maxillary central incisor spontaneously erupts after removal of the supernumerary tooth but takes significant period of time. The aim of this case report is to present a case of spontaneous eruption of impacted maxillary permanent left central incisor after removal of multiple impacted supernumerary teeth.

Introduction

A smile of a child is a packaged sunshine and rainbows. The impacted maxillary central incisor is a significant matter of aesthetic and practical concern for an individual.^[1] This lack of eruption could be due to a number of causes, however the most common cause cited for delayed eruption is the presence of a supernumerary tooth in the pre-maxillary region.^[2,3,4] The prevalence of supernumerary teeth for permanent dentition is between 0.5 and 5.3% and in primary dentition is between 0.2 and 0.8% in various populations. Also, prevalence of nonsyndromic multiple supernumeraries is less than 1 percent of all hyperdontia cases which themselves have a rather small prevalence. In addition, the gender wise prevalence of supernumerary teeth or hyperdontia shows that these teeth are predominantly seen in males than in females.^[5,6] Spontaneous eruption of impacted maxillary incisors occurs in 54-76% of cases when supernumerary tooth is removed and there is enough space in the dental arch. However, research data indicate that the spontaneous eruption of impacted maxillary incisor may take up to 3 years and sometimes orthodontic treatment is necessary to achieve adequate alignment of the erupted tooth in the dental arch.^[7,8,9]

This case report aims to present a case of multiple impacted supernumerary teeth along with impacted permanent central incisor and its spontaneous eruption after surgical removal of impacted supernumeraries.

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A Case Report

A 10-year-old boy reported to the department of paediatric and preventive dentistry at Career Post Graduate Institute of Dental Sciences and Hospital, Lucknow with the chief complain of missing permanent maxillary central incisor. The child was healthy with no history of medical or dental trauma or extraction. On clinical examination, a missing permanent maxillary left central incisor was seen with no arch discrepancy in maxillary and mandibular arch (FIG 2.). A tooth was seen on rugae area who's only a tip was visible (FIG 1). Thus, the provisional diagnosis of ectopic eruption of permanent left central incisor was made.

Fig. 1. Pre-op Intra Oral View Showing

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Fig 2. Frontal View Palatally Erupting Supernumerary Teeth.

The patient was further advised for an OPG (FIG 3). On radiographic examination it was revealed that the permanent maxillary left central incisor was impacted and the palatally erupting teeth was a supernumerary tooth. A CBCT was then advised to rule out chances of other impacted supernumerary teeth. The CBCT revealed 3 impacted supernumerary teeth along with impacted permanent left central incisor (FIG 4 (a,b&c)) first impacted supernumerary teeth is placed inverted and approaching nasal floor (FIG 5). The second impacted supernumerary was a mesiodens in midline superior to central incisors. Third impacted supernumerary lies above right permanent central incisor.

Fig. 3. Initial OPG

Fig. 4. CBCT Showing Impacted Supernumerary with Impacted Left Central Incisor.

Fig 5. Inverted Supernumerary Approaching the Nasal Floor

The treatment plan was explained to the patient and his parents and consent was taken for the extraction of supernumerary tooth surgically and it was decided to leave central incisor without any interventions for spontaneous eruption. Before the beginning of the surgical phase, full mouth oral prophylaxis was done, and the patient was advised to go for a regular medical check-up, his complete blood picture routine investigation was done. Surgery was planned for the next day. Under local anesthesia, crevicular and vertical incisions were given using surgical blade number #15, and #11 and a full-thickness mucoperiosteal flap on the palatal side was raised using a periosteal elevator (FIG 6). Mesiodens was extracted first and then window was created to expose and extract inverted supernumerary teeth (FIG 7 & 8). Mucoperiosteal flap was then approximated and sutured with 3-0 black silk suture (FIG 11). Instructions were given not to disturb the surgical site till healing.

Fig. 6. Palatal Flap Raised Was raised

Fig. 7. Window is Created

Fig. 8. Inverted Tooth was Exposed

Fig. 9. Post Extraction

Fig 12. 5 Month Follow up Picture Showing more than 2/3rd Root Completion

Fig. 10. All 3 Supernumerary Teeth Were

Fig 13. 11 Months Follow Up

Fig. 11. Interrupted Sutures Placed Extracted

Fig 14. Showing Erupting Left Central Incisor At 9 Months

After 1 week, sutures were removed. Patient was kept under follow up. At 5 months 2/3rd root was completed but tooth was not erupted (FIG 12). At 9 month follow up spontaneous eruption of permanent left central incisor was seen with root almost completed and only incisal 1/3rd of crown was visible clinically (13&14) and further on 12 months follow up the root is completed and 2/3rd of the crown visible clinically (15, 16,) and on 14th month follow up root formation is completed with apex closed (17). The tooth is not yet in the occlusion.

Fig 15. 12 Month Follow Up

Fig 16. 12 Month Follow Up

Fig 17. 14th Month Follow up

Discussion

Tooth eruption involves creating a pathway through bone resorption, interradicular bone formation, root growth, and bone apposition, all directed by the dental follicle. Impaction refers to a tooth that is unable or unlikely to erupt into its normal functional position within the expected time period. Failure of complete eruption of maxillary incisors is one of the most common complications of the presence of supernumerary teeth in the anterior maxilla^[10,11]. The literature reports that 80% to 90% of all supernumerary teeth occurs in the maxilla. The greatest proportion are found in maxillary anterior region.

Multiple supernumerary teeth in the absence of any syndrome are not very common. There are only a few published cases of nonsyndromic association of multiple supernumerary teeth. A single supernumerary occurs in 76%-86% of cases; double supernumeraries occur in 12%-23% of cases and multiple supernumerary teeth <1%. The optimal

timing of surgical removal of unerupted anterior supernumerary teeth is often conjectural. An atraumatic careful surgical procedure is important to prevent any damage to the developing roots, which could result in dilacerations and further impede eruption. The majority of impacted maxillary central incisor spontaneously erupts after removal of the supernumerary tooth but takes significant period of time^[12,13,14]. The pooled estimate for the successful eruption of the incisor after removal of the supernumerary was 57.6%^[15,16].

In present case multiple impacted supernumerary teeth along with impacted left permanent central incisor have been observed. A conclusive diagnosis and management of supernumerary teeth should be made only through clinical and radiographic analysis. With upcoming advanced technologies, the use of cone beam computed tomography (CBCT) can be done to locate the exact position of tooth. In present case CBCT was performed which revealed 3 impacted supernumeraries with impacted left permanent central incisor with incomplete root formation. One supernumerary was inverted and approximating nasal floor. Surgical removal of all supernumerary teeth was planned and it was decided to leave the central incisor for spontaneous eruption. Patient was kept under follow ups and 9 months after surgical removal eruption of central incisor was seen with 2/3rd of root completion and only incisal edge of crown was clinically visible. After 12-month root completion was seen with 1/3rd of the crown visible clinically. on 14th month follow up root formation is completed with apex closed. The tooth is not in occlusion yet. Thus, further orthodontic treatment may be required for that patient is still under follow up.

Conclusion

It is important for the dentist to be aware of the causes of unerupted teeth and consider proper timing for the referral and surgical intervention. Supernumerary teeth may result in the non-eruption of adjacent permanent incisors. In cases where spontaneous eruption fails to occur. It is important to recognise the cause. In this case spontaneous eruption of left permanent central incisor was seen after surgical removal of multiple supernumerary teeth.

References

1. Agarwal S, Pandey SN, Khan SA, Sharma A. From Disharmony to Harmony: Management of Impacted Central Incisor with the Combined Surgical and Orthodontic Approach. *Pediatr Dent*. 2019 Jun 1;2(1):1-4.
2. Lin YT. Treatment of an impacted dilacerated maxillary central incisor. *American journal of orthodontics and dentofacial orthopedics*. 1999 Apr 1;115(4):406-9.
3. Leyland L, Batra P, Wong F, Llewelyn R. A retrospective evaluation of the eruption of impacted permanent incisors after extraction of supernumerary teeth. *Journal of Clinical Pediatric Dentistry*. 2006 Apr 1;30(3):225-32.
4. Brin I, Zilberman Y, Azaz B. The unerupted maxillary central incisor: review of its etiology and treatment. *ASDC J Dent Child*;49(5):352-357. 1982.
5. Gregg TA, Kinirons MJ. The effect of the position and orientation of unerupted supernumerary teeth on eruption and displacement of permanent incisors. *Int J Pediatr Dent*;1:3-7. 1991.
6. Ravn JJ, Fibæk B. Impaction of central incisors associated with supernumerary teeth. *Dent Abstr*-16:568. 1971.
7. Moradinejad M, Hashemi Ashtiani A, Rakhshan V. Multiple nonsyndromic unerupted supernumerary teeth: a report of a rare case.

- Case Reports in Dentistry. 2022;2022(1):4063856.
8. Nazif MM, Ruffalo RC, Zullo T. Impacted supernumerary teeth: a survey of 50 cases. JADA;106:201-4. 1983.
 9. Mason C, Azam N, Holt RD, Rule DC. A retrospective study of unerupted maxillary incisors associated with supernumerary teeth. Br J Oral Maxillofac Surg;38:62-65. 2000.
 10. Crawford LB. Impacted maxillary central incisor in mixed dentition treatment. Am J OrthodDentofacOrthop 1997; 112(1): 1-7.
 11. Garvey M.T., Barry H.J., Blake M. Supernumerary teeth - an overview of classification, diagnosis and management. J Canad Dent Assoc 1999; 65: 612-6.
 12. Mitchell L., Bennett T.G. Supernumerary teeth causing delayed eruption. Br J Orthod 1992; 19: 41-6.
 13. Aizenbud, D.; Front, Y.P. An Impacted Malformed Primary Maxillary Central Incisor Diagnosed as a Compound Odontoma. J. Clin. Pediatr. Dent. 2008, 33, 161-166. [CrossRef] [PubMed].
 14. Ullah RI, Dwivedi S, Mishra A, Upadhyay VK. Management of Multiple Supernumerary Teeth Followed by Fixed Appliance Therapy: A Case Report. Journal of South Asian Association of Pediatric Dentistry. 2023 Aug 29;6(2):77-81.
 15. Hattab FN, Yassin OM, Rawashdeh MA. Supernumerary teeth: Report of three cases and review of literature. ASDC J Dent Child;61:382-393. 1994.
 16. Seehra J, Mortaja K, Wazwaz F, Papageorgiou SN, Newton JT, Cobourne MT. Interventions to facilitate the successful eruption of impacted maxillary incisor teeth due to the presence of a supernumerary: A systematic review and meta-analysis. American Journal of Orthodontics and Dentofacial Orthopedics. 2023 May 1;163(5):594-608.

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